

Delivering Pleasure: The Personalisation of Running Shoes

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Abstract: There is a need for better fitting and performing running shoes than is currently available to the consumer. Personalisation is a potential method of delivering this required improvement but companies' current focus is primarily on aesthetic design, tailored using the internet. Aesthetics do not appear to be the consumers' primary interest when purchasing shoes and a large number are also reluctant to purchase online; preferring to purchase from specialist running stores. These stores deliver the advice consumers need to make an informed decision and provide direct interaction with the potential purchase, fostering product attachment. In this paper an investigation into how to implement a successful running shoe personalisation experience is reported. Current literature was consulted, and focus groups, interviews and surveys were conducted. These targeted both qualitative and quantitative data, exploring consumer running shoe purchase preferences, opinions of current personalisation services and their desired experience. It was established that a personalisation service designed adhering to outlined interaction experience design guidelines and offering the consumer suitable options, primarily comfort and performance, gave the greatest opportunity for success.

Key words: *Running shoe, experience, personalisation, service, retail.*

1. Introduction

In recent years there has been a steady increase in the number of people running [1] and running shoes are the largest selling shoe within the sports footwear market [2]. Research has identified that many of these runners require better fitting and performing footwear than is currently available [3 – 5]; personalisation is one potential method of delivering running shoes that better meet consumers' needs [6].

There are a large number of sports footwear personalisation services: Nike iD, mi adidas, Puma Mongolian BBQ and Your Reebok are some of the most prominent. The majority of these offer a primarily aesthetic online service with a limited number of 'flagship' in store services. Nike and adidas provide some basic options relating to comfort and performance; however, their shoes provide no features in these areas that cannot be found across a standard shoe range.

Pine and Gilmore [7] suggest that the experience provided may differentiate one service from another; in some cases consumers may pay more for a more limited service because the experience is so much more enjoyable. To

stimulate product attachment designers should deliver an experience that engages consumers, allowing them to express themselves, in the appropriate areas, to a suitable degree [8]. Norman [9] believes current personalisation services fail to achieve this, presenting the consumer with a large number of alternative options in undesirable areas. Using the internet to deliver these options may also be an issue; many consumers prefer purchasing shoes in stores [10], where they are able to try the footwear and receive advice. This immersive experience reduces the consumer's insecurities and fosters product attachment [11].

The author was able to find limited information on the subject of how to deliver a rich running shoe personalisation experience. The main aim of this research, therefore, was to establish design guidelines to deliver this experience. In order to achieve this, the following questions were addressed.

1. How do consumers currently purchase running shoes?
2. What do consumers think of current sports footwear personalisation experiences?
3. What are the guidelines for delivering a rich experience to a consumer?

2. Literature Review

2.1. Consumer running shoe purchase

2.1.1. Selection criteria

5038 participants in a 16km street race in Berne, Switzerland in 1984 completed a survey about their shoe selection criteria [12]. There was a bias towards young males and regular runners. They were asked to rate eight different shoe selection criteria (see table 1).

Table 1. 1984 Berne street race participants ranking of 8 shoe selection criteria [12]

	Criteria	Scale of Relative Value*
1	Orthopedically correct construction of the running shoe	2.71
2	Fit/comfort	2.65
3	Slip-resistance/profile of sole	2.12
4	Durability	1.88
5	Low weight	1.53
6	Cost	1.22
7	Appearance (colour/model)	0.55
8	Used by champion runners	0.38

*Scale of relative value is from 0 (not important) to 3 (very important)

Comfort and performance related aspects all rank higher than the more superficial aspects, such as appearance. These findings concur with those of Collazzo, who conducted an investigation of consumer problems when shopping for footwear [13]. Stuhlfaut and Sullivan [4] asked 204 frequent runners, running over 40 miles a week, to rate how fashionable they liked their shoes to be on a seven-point likert scale (0 - I don't care how they look to 7 - very fashionable). 62% of participants scored three or less, indicating a lack of importance in the aesthetic of their footwear choice.

This is not to say appearance does not have a role to play in running shoes. They are designed to elicit a stronger semantic response than that of, for example, a leisure shoe [14]. They are presented as functional shoes, fit for

purpose to encourage consumers to perceive them as comfortable, high-performance footwear. This is also, perhaps, part of the reason why runners appear reluctant to purchase online; they like to reinforce their expectations by engaging with the footwear.

After purchase consumers often make additions to their shoes to improve comfort and performance; Stuhlfaut & Sullivan [4] identified that, out of 196 frequent runners, 15% used orthotics prescribed by a doctor with a further 6% buying insoles. From the 21,326 runners who either test or applied to test shoes for New Balance, 2613 (12%) wear orthotics or insoles [3]; a sizeable percentage of people from a large sample. This supports research indicating that standard footwear may not provide runners with the comfort and performance characteristics they desire [15, 16].

The findings of this research suggest that comfort and performance is of high importance to runners and that standard footwear cannot always cater for this need. Existing personalisation services do not provide options that target this potential gap and, as a consequence, are not competitive with standard footwear in the large running shoe market.

2.1.2. Purchase Location

Limited research was identified concerning consumers' preferred running shoe purchase location. In 2007, 113 regular runners participating in a study [4] purchased new running shoes. Of these, 40% purchased from a specialist running store, in comparison with 26% who bought online. The remaining 34% bought their running shoes from either a standard retail shop, discount retailer, catalogues or other miscellaneous sources. The internet is of increasing popularity for purchases [10], offering access to a wide range of footwear at cheaper prices. Based on this survey, many consumers still appear to prefer the experience of going to a specialist store. Further research is desirable in this area.

2.1.3. Sources of Advice

Stuhlfaut and Sullivan [4] found that to inform their purchase decisions, runners used a range of sources; of the 113 participants, 25% used the internet and just under 25% consulted store assistants, with magazines and recommendations from friends accounting for around 10% each. Other unspecified sources of information were used by nearly 13% of participants and 8% bought without any advice. Additional research is necessary to establish the preferred source of advice; these results highlight the importance of ensuring the consumer is able to make an informed decision.

2.1.4. Summary

The focus of the current running shoe personalisation services is primarily aesthetics, but consumers appear to be most interested in the comfort and performance aspects of their footwear. To increase confidence in their purchase many runners like to visit a specialist store and speak face to face with a store assistant. The existing services are situated predominantly online, denying the consumer the opportunity to familiarise themselves with their potential purchase. There is limited research in this area, most of it focuses on regular runners, and some is rather dated. Further investigation is required.

2.2. Current feedback for personalisation experiences

Little consumer feedback was uncovered concerning running shoe personalisation; therefore, in this section the focus is on feedback from consumers concerning sports footwear personalisation services.

2.2.1. Online

In 2007 Yessin [17] recruited three participants who reviewed two of the current footwear personalisation services: NikeiD and Reebok Custom, the latter now re-branded as Your Reebok. The participants had never personalised a product before and each received a \$50 payment, allowing them to purchase their own footwear, providing a more thorough review of the services.

The Nike service was used by two of the three participants because of their allegiance to the brand. The remaining participant started with the Puma Mongolian BBQ service but switched to the Reebok service because the Puma site was very slow. Outlined below are the main problems the participants encountered:

- **Flawed user interface:** participants encountered problems with the usability of the websites.
- **No advice on their colour/material decisions:** participants had to contact friends/family, for advice.
- **Not enough/too much choice:** different aspects of the services offered inappropriate levels of choice.
- **No tactile feedback:** participants were unable to feel what the shoe/material choices would be like.
- **Poor/inaccurate shoe preview image:** finished shoes were not as displayed.
- **Minimal/inappropriate contact during wait for delivery:** participants received little contact, of a detached tone, whilst waiting to receive their footwear, with statements such as ‘All sales are final’.
- **Poor delivery system:** one participant never received his footwear.

These problems served to reduce consumers’ confidence in the service and minimise the likelihood of purchase. Additionally, the consumer was made to feel insecure after they had committed to purchase, reducing the possibility of them utilising the service again. The user interface issues should have been avoided; Jordan states that when people encounter a usable product they are no longer pleasantly surprised, it is expected [18]. Yessin provides potential solutions to another of the identified problems; providing advice to support colour/material decisions. An in store experience was the most feasible way, Yessin believed, of remedying some of the above issues, including, importantly, a lack of tactile feedback.

2.2.2. In store Experience

Adidas

When visiting in 2007, Yessin [17] was surprised by the technology utilized by the mi adidas service; she believed it would be more advanced, considering it was labeled as, primarily, a comfort and performance service. She also felt that the service was poorly advertised and did not provide value for money; the shoes were nearly double the price of the standard mass produced equivalents, yet consumers were unable to tailor the fit to a greater degree.

Puma

There were differing opinions regarding the Puma Mongolian BBQ service but they were largely negative; the system was out of order when Yessin visited the store so a detailed analysis was not completed. Herd [19] felt it was well designed to encourage use and conversation, though the ease with which the system was left in disarray lessened the experience for subsequent users. Yessin believed that the self-service system resulted in a lack of warmth in the service. However, she liked the fact that you were able to feel the different material swatches; the tactile element improving her experience. Herd concurred, though felt some of the swatches were unrepresentative of the final product [19]. Additionally, the service was found to be unintuitive and disappointingly absent of memorabilia: Herd did not even receive an image of the product to show family/friends. The contact during the wait for the shoes to be delivered was equally dissatisfying, leaving her not wanting to share her experience with others.

Nike

Yessin found the NikeiD service a more positive experience [17]. The advance booking of an appointment ensured you would receive 45 minutes with staff who were trained in colour choices, allowing plenty of time and increasing confidence in decision making. The service was also exclusive; there were very few of these stores worldwide and you were able to personalise shoes that you could not online. The provision of a business card with the chosen design printed on it enhanced the experience, giving the consumer something that they were able to show to friends/family during the wait for delivery of their shoes.

2.2.3. Summary

Although a substantial amount of feedback could not be found on the current personalisation services, this information demonstrates areas in which retailers fail and succeed in delivering a desirable experience for consumers. Although these studies focus on leisure shoes, where aesthetics may be of primary importance [14], it appears the consumers still desire physical interaction in the design process. The importance of maintaining contact and providing memorabilia are also underlined, as are the benefits of store assistants. More assistance with design choices, when utilising an online service, would help minimise consumer insecurities. Further research is needed, specifically looking at running shoes, if an effective personalisation experience is to be delivered.

2.3. Delivering a rich experience

Experiences can be used as a way of differentiating between similar services [20]. Pine and Gilmore [6] provide five key experience design principles.

- **Theme the experience:** Deliver a strong consistent theme for the whole experience. Puma's footwear personalisation service is the Mongolian BBQ, and this theme is followed consistently online (see figure 1a).
- **Harmonise impressions with positive cues:** Cues can be anything that reinforces the theme of the experience. An example of this is the presentation of the in store Nike iD service (see figure 1b).

- **Eliminate negative cues:** It is equally important to ensure negative cues are minimised e.g. how a store assistant obtains particular sensitive information without causing discomfort, for example, consumers' body mass. Recording it electronically is one possibility.
- **Mix in memorabilia:** If an experience is engaging, consumers will want memorabilia. With the in store Nike iD service the retailer presents the consumer with an image of their design printed on a card at the point of payment. This reminds them of the experience and they are able to show it to others as they await delivery of their shoes.
- **Engage all five senses:** A good experience should engage sight, hearing, taste, smell and touch. The material swatches supplied by the in store Puma Mongolian BBQ service provide an example of engaging sight and touch when it is not possible to present the final product.

Figure. 1a (left) The Puma Mongolian BBQ service has a consistent theme throughout [21]
 Figure. 1b (right) The in store Nike iD service; the walls are encased with shoes in a variety of colours, communicating the 'endless' possibilities

Considering these guidelines with respect to current running shoe personalisation services reveals a number of reasons for potential failure. Some of the themes are not strong or consistent (see figure. 2a), positive cues are not present to support the consumer with certain decisions (see figure. 2b), and the consumer receives only one email confirmation whilst they wait for their shoes to arrive. The major problem, however, is certain senses, including, most importantly, touch, are not engaged. It was identified previously that comfort is important when purchasing running shoes; not being able to try the shoes makes it difficult to provide the desired experience.

Figure. 2a (left) The Mi Adidas online service is plain; there is a lack of theme [22]
 Figure. 2b (right) Nike iD offers the consumer a choice of outsole but doesn't provide any information to support their decision [23]

Forlizzi [24] defined a set of guidelines for designing rich experiences for interaction design, listed below:

- Designers should understand each individual user is unique and deliver a product that allows them to define themselves as individuals.
- Interactions provided should be carefully considered to ensure they deliver value.
- Researching the potential users and the context of use is essential.

The current services offer a variety of aesthetic options allowing consumers to define themselves as individuals, however, initial research demonstrates comfort and performance options to be of greater importance to consumers. This illustrates that companies are not targeting the potential users appropriately; providing an unnecessary amount of personalisation in an area of lesser interest. Adhering to the above principles, within the company's economic constraints, may help to avoid the majority of problems encountered by consumers with current personalisation services.

This literature review has given an indication of how to design a rich experience for a running shoe personalisation service. Further consumer feedback is desirable in the following areas:

1. Running shoe purchase preferences
2. Opinion of current personalisation services
3. Desired experience

3. Methodology

It was desirable to acquire both qualitative and quantitative data to establish consumers' needs in a personalisation system. Quantitative data will help to support/contest the findings in the current literature and qualitative detail will provide the specific details necessary to design the experience. These data were collected using a variety of methods identified as appropriate; focus groups, questionnaires and interviews.

3.1. Focus Group

Twenty running shoe owners were chosen as participants; they were split into four separate sessions:

- Male Runners *6 participants*
- Female Runners *4 participants*
- Male Non-Runners *6 participants*
- Female Non-Runners *4 participants*

'Runners' were defined as people who ran at least twice a week. 'Non-Runners' used their running shoes predominantly for activities other than running. This division was used to group people with similar running shoe use, without greatly increasing the number of focus groups needed. Separate focus groups were run for the different sexes to encourage a comfortable environment in which everyone could contribute [25]. The focus groups were designed to provide information for all three of the outlined objectives.

3.2. Questionnaire

Forty-two participants (31 males and 11 females) were solicited at the London Marathon Exposition; over 70% ran between 11 and 40 miles a week. The questionnaire was designed to focus primarily on consumers' running shoe purchase preferences and desired experience.

3.3. Online Questionnaire

The aims of the online questionnaire were to understand consumers' running shoe use and investigate the Nike iD service. Participants were recruited primarily from the Loughborough University student population. Forty-one participants completed the survey in total; there were no exclusion criteria with respect to their running habits. Participants were asked to design running shoes using the Nike iD service and then answer questions on their experience and running shoe usage.

3.4. Interviews

The interviews were carried out in a specialist running store, identified in the literature as the most popular purchase location. There were two main intentions of the interviews; to obtain an overview of the service provided and to understand consumers' purchase decisions in these stores. Interviews were carried out with five assistants and four customers at four different stores within the United Kingdom. Semi-structured interviews were used to allow for flexibility.

The data captured by these methods are presented in the following section.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section the key findings from the research activities with respect to the outlined objectives are detailed.

4.1. Running Shoe purchase preferences

4.1.1. Selection Criteria

Questionnaire participants were asked to rank different selection criteria when purchasing running shoes. The results identified comfort and performance aspects to be the most important (see table 2); the other research activities supported this finding. Participants' priorities were finding shoes that fitted, supported them appropriately and kept them injury free. Of those participants questioned, some mentioned they would be happy to spend more on their shoes if they felt they had received good customer service. These findings support the need for a personalisation experience that focuses on delivering supportive comfortable running shoes.

4.1.2. Purchase Location

The results from the questionnaire support the findings from the literature; the specialist running store was the most popular purchase location and the internet was also selected by many participants (see table 3). A consensus was not established with the other research activities. General sportswear chains were popular, however many of the runners stated they would first go to a specialist running store to find a suitable shoe, then use the chain or internet to purchase it more cheaply. Some of those participants questioned were hesitant to buy using the internet because they were unable to try on the shoes and did not want to go through the inconvenience of returning them. These results reinforce the importance of the consumer being comfortable with their selection before making a purchase, as outlined in the literature, but also show that consumers seek good value for their purchase.

Table 2. Questionnaire participants' rank of selection criteria when purchasing running shoes

Factor	Rank									Total Votes
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	
Support	18	14	5		2		1	1		41
Comfort	17	11	9							37
Injury Prevention	10	7	11	6	3	1	1			39
Price	2	7	10	12	2	4	1	2		40
Aesthetics	2	4	1	3	7	5	9	4		35
Brand	1	3	1	5	5	5	7	7		34
Durability	1	2	5	7	7	1	1	1	1	26
Technology		4	3	1	3	3	5	11		30
Other: Weight		1								1
Other: Width						1				1

Table 3. Questionnaire participants' running shoe purchase locations

Gender	Running Shoe Purchase Location						
	General Sportswear Chain	Specialist Running Shop	Discount Warehouse	Department Store	Manufacturer's Store	Internet	Other – Trade Show
Males	5	24	1	1	3	14	1
Females	1	10	0	0	1	2	0
Overall	6	34	1	1	4	16	1

4.1.3. Sources of Advice

Store assistants were the preferred source of advice for questionnaire participants (see table 4). There were also several other sources consulted by participants when purchasing running shoes; reviews on the internet and magazines were popular options. Participants stated that they felt reassured when they talked to someone, family or friends were also often consulted. The results showed that participants found advice important in helping instill confidence in their decisions. Store assistants' popularity may be a key factor in the specialist running stores delivery of a rich experience.

Table 4. Questionnaire participants' sources of advice when purchasing running shoes

Gender	Sources of Advice							
	Don't Seek Advice	Friends/Family	Coach	Store Assistant	Internet	Magazine	Other - Runners	Other
Males	4	4	6	19	7	11	1	1
Females		4	2	8	1	2		
Overall	4	8	8	27	8	13	1	1

4.2. Consumer opinion of current personalisation services

In this section consumer interest and opinion of the current personalisation services is explored. The research activities demonstrated a clear interest in the personalisation of running shoes, with many participants experiencing fitting and performance issues with their current footwear. A small number of participants were attracted to aesthetic personalisation but the primary focus was the comfort and performance characteristics. Most participants would not use the current personalisation services because they felt that they did not provide the array of comfort and performance options they desired. Providing this would greatly enhance the likelihood of a positive consumer experience.

This research provided an insight into consumers' opinions of the Nike iD personalisation service. Participants found, in many cases, not enough information was provided to make choices; this left consumers doubting their selections. It was, however, considered, easy to use, helping to provide an enjoyable experience. A consensus was not established concerning whether participants would use the service again, price was a deterrent for many of the participants. Despite offering more options than those available in a specialist running store, participants appear to be more accepting of the price premium in the latter, strengthening the opinion that the experience received can be the differentiating factor.

4.3. Consumer's desired experience

As mentioned in section 4.1, many participants in these research activities found advice from store assistants to be important. This finding was reinforced in the interviews with consumers, who also detailed the following important factors in providing an enjoyable experience:

- A welcoming environment, facilitated often by just a greeting, made the consumers feel more comfortable and stay longer.
- The ability to use a treadmill and the gait analysis strengthened consumer's confidence in their decision.
- Consumers did not want to feel rushed (some liked to spend up to 40 minutes in the store).

Some of the interviewees also stated they were happy to pay more for this experience and did not consider the discounts they might receive elsewhere. This result may have been biased because they were in a store at the time of asking but the finding concurs with the evidence in the literature.

The specialist running store was identified as a trusted shoe purchase location, providing an excellent overall service. During the interviews with the assistants they outlined that which, they believed, were key principles in delivering this experience.

- Ensuring consumers were welcomed and comfortable.
- Empowering consumers; their opinion was actively encouraged during the decision making process.
- They spend an amount of time with each consumer that they felt suitable.
- They provide extra help, specific to each consumer: recommending suitable insoles, indicating subtle differences between the brands and providing advice to improve a consumer's gait are examples of this.

In the case of a specialist store, following the above principles delivers many potential benefits:

- They are able to charge more for the shoes, and one store actually charged for the experience.

- They maintain a loyal customer base. This may, in part, be because a consumer exchanges so much information that they are reluctant to change to another provider [26].
- The consumer purchases a shoe that they have developed a bond with so returns are rare. Shoes that are returned are normally due to faults with the shoes rather than the fit.

5. Conclusion

There is clearly the potential for successful personalisation of running shoes but consumers are not currently experiencing a service that meets their expectations. Companies are not following the outlined rules of experience design, delivering services that are not appropriately tailored to the consumers' needs. Consumers also want to feel confident in their choices and emotionally connected to their purchase. This appears to be something that is difficult to establish if purchasing over the internet; the consumer is unable to engage all the necessary senses to develop this bond. This is not to say the online experience cannot be improved; Nike's online shoe finder [27] demonstrates how interactive decision aids are able to assist consumers in making informed decisions with little effort [28]. Consumers are guided through a series of comfort and performance questions, empowering them and helping to increase their confidence in the recommended standard footwear.

In addition to following the experience design guidelines outlined in section 2.3, below is a list of specific rules that should be adhered to when designing a running shoe personalisation service.

- Understand the consumers' desired comfort and performance choices.
- Provide suitable information to help inform the consumers' decisions, in a suitable format.
- Make the consumer feel at ease and empowered.
- Treat each consumer like an individual.
- Ensure the consumer feels part of the process until the shoes are delivered and keep in touch beyond.

Future research is necessary in two particular areas to implement a successful running shoe personalisation experience. The first, the type and level of comfort and performance options a consumer desires must be identified. Additionally, specifically how to deliver these options must be established in order to ensure the consumer is offered the best opportunity to become attached to their potential purchase [8]. Initial research has been undertaken within the Elite to High Street project [29] and externally [30, 31].

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